

FEATURES OF THE IMMUNE SYSTEM OF WOMEN DURING SPORTS ACTIVITIES

Raimov Khamid Soatovich

Senior Lecturer at the Department of Sports Management
Termez State University

Annotation: The article provides a brief description of diametrically opposed views on the role of physical activity on human health, whether health-improving or negative. In recent decades, the functional unity of the central nervous system, endocrine and immune systems has been established, which are defined as the neuroendocrine-immune system. The nature of the system's reaction under conditions of physical activity depends not only on their magnitude and intensity, but also on the intensity of their psycho-emotional accompaniment, which is typical for modern elite sports.

Key words: modern sport, immunity, female athletes, specifics of the female body.

Introduction. Physical activity and physical exercise are integral components of a healthy lifestyle [1, 3, 4]. They contribute to the prevention of many diseases, promotion of health and harmonious personal development. A person's physical development, the most important indicator of his health, is a sensitive indicator of both positive and negative socio-economic changes [2, 5].

Among representatives of medicine, there are diametrically opposed points of view on the role of physical activity in the lives of people of different ages. Thus, if the health-improving effect of heavy physical activity has not been proven, there are more arguments in favor of the widespread use of moderate and regular training loads [6, 7]. According to the authors, such physical activity helps to improve the

psychological state against the background of increased physical development, reduce the level of anxiety, increase self-esteem and tolerance to stressors [9, 10].

The relationship between physical activity during sports activities and the immune system is coordinated through the neuroendocrine system. Moreover, each component of this system is functionally interdependent in ensuring the final adaptive result [8].

Over the past decades, the functional unity of the central nervous system, endocrine and immune systems has been established, which formed the basis for the development of the science of neuroimmunology [11, 14]. The two-way relationship between the central nervous system, endocrine and immune systems is defined by the concept of “neuroendocrine immune system”.

Physical training and competitive loads are to some extent stressful for the athlete’s body and involve adaptation processes and the immune system. The basis for maintaining homeostasis under stress is the coordination of functions through the hypothalamic-pituitary-adrenal system [12, 13]. It has been established that if a stress factor (psycho-emotional, physical stress) is perceived by the body as negative, the type and degree of neuroendocrine activation can cause suppression of the functions of the immune system. When a stress factor is perceived as positive, the neuroendocrine system can stimulate the functions of the immune system [14, 17].

Physical activity is considered as a biologically beneficial factor. However, the degree of reaction of the lymphoid system depends not only on the strength (intensity and duration) of physical activity, but also on the intensity of the accompanying psycho-emotional stress, which is typical, in particular, for modern elite sports [15,16].

According to J. Witkin, “...men and women may be born equal, but they are by no means the same, especially when it comes to stress.” The author believes that, along with “negative” and “positive” stress factors, it is necessary to consider “female” stress, due to the specific physiological and mental reactions of the female

body to prolonged exposure to stress. A woman's body is exposed to two "types" of stress factors, such as ordinary ones, characteristic of men and women, and additional, purely female ones, characteristic either only of women, or occurring more often in them than in men. Thus, there are symptoms caused by stress that appear only in women: amenorrhea, premenstrual syndrome, postpartum depression, infertility, depression associated with menopause.

Disorders that are not specifically female, but are more common in women - anorexia, anxiety attacks, bulimia, depression. All long-term stress cannot be properly controlled and is therefore more dangerous. They reduce the immunoreactivity of a woman's body. The immunostimulating effect is obvious with optimally selected physical activity, individually corresponding to the functional capabilities of the athlete's body.

At the same time, when considering the causes of diseases in athletes, it is necessary to emphasize the danger of developing a state of overtraining of the body, especially among athletes in elite sports as a result of loads exceeding the functional and psycho-emotional capabilities of the body.

Overtraining as a pathological condition of the body manifests itself in overstrain of the functions (their disturbances) of the body systems and, above all, the central nervous and endocrine ones. As a consequence, the mechanisms of neurohumoral regulation of the functions of body systems, including the immune system, are disrupted.

During intense training and competitive activity of an athlete, the immune system, like other systems of the body, experiences chronic physical overstrain, which manifests itself in an increase in the susceptibility of the athlete's body to genetically foreign factors, in particular to infection. The immunological reactivity of the athletes' body has not yet been sufficiently reflected in the specialized scientific literature. At the same time, there is enough material that confirms the connection between the reproductive system and the immune system.

Gender differences in the immune system of men and women, which manifest themselves not only during periods of hormonal changes, but also in other periods of life, determine the relevance of studying the effect of sex steroids on the immune system. Literature data indicate that the peak incidence of autoimmune pathology in women occurs during periods of hormonal changes - either puberty, early postpartum, or menopause.

It should be noted that in women, both the humoral and cellular components of the immune response are more pronounced than in men (the immune response is longer, the threshold for its development is lower, and the peak of antibodies is higher). This confirms the existence of a phenomenon called immunological sexual dimorphism. It manifests itself primarily in a more pronounced reaction of the female body to exogenous invasive factors, such as infection, foreign intervention.

In women, a higher level of T-helper cells and a lower level of T-suppressor cells were detected, that is, the activation of the B-system of immunity is more pronounced, which explains the above-mentioned discrepancies in the composition of antibodies.

At the same time, women demonstrate a stronger reaction to transplants; they have a more active cell-mediated immune response to viral infections.

Thus, the female body reacts more acutely to all exogenous factors that are included to one degree or another in the vital activity of the body than the male body. This can be traced at the level of both systemic and secretory (local) immunity.

In the process of evolution, an immune system has been formed in the body, capable of creating and maintaining protective programs, individually selected in relation to antigens, and, if necessary, recalling these programs from the “archive” and using them in an enhanced mode.

The structure of the immune system is represented by the organs of the immune system that provide acquired immunity. They are usually divided into central (primary) and peripheral (secondary).

The central organs of the immune system include the thymus gland (thymus) and bone marrow; to the peripheral - the spleen, lymph nodes, lymphopharyngeal ring, lymphoid tissue of the mucous membranes, as well as lymphoid cells circulating in the peripheral blood.

Conclusions. The data presented above indicate the relationship between physical activity during sports activities, its psycho-emotional accompaniment and the immune system, which are coordinated by the neuroendocrine-immune system. Differences have been established in the immune systems of men and women.

According to C. J. Grossman, in women, both the humoral and cellular components of the immune response confirm the existence of the phenomenon of immunological sexual dimorphism. The direct effect of sex steroid hormones on the organs and tissues of the immune system due to specific receptors for progesterone and estrogens has been established. However, there is practically no scientific literature on the specifics of the immunoreactivity of the body of female athletes in different phases of the menstrual cycle during cyclic changes in hormonal status, on the impact on the functions of the leading systems of the body, the health of athletes and their performance. Therefore, deepening research in this direction is of great importance in the practice of modern elite sports - identifying the degree of adaptation of the endocrine and immune systems to physical activity, assessing the effectiveness of the training process of female athletes, as well as timely prevention of diseases associated with the professional activities of female athletes.

References:

1. Abdiravupovich, K. A. (2021). Features of the training process of volleyball players of various qualifications. *European Journal of Life Safety and Stability* (2660-9630), 7, 95-98.
2. Abdiravupovich, K. A. (2021). Features of the training process of volleyball players of various qualifications. *European Journal of Life Safety and Stability* (2660-9630), 7, 95-98.

3. Abdullayev, Y. M. (2024). Formation of abilities and skills with track and peace athletics exercises. *Modern Scientific Research International Scientific Journal*, 2(2), 123-130.
4. Alikulovich, M. K., & Yuldashevich, T. D. (2020). Development of physical training skills and formation of willpower qualities in extracurricular activities. *European Journal of Research and Reflection in Educational Sciences Vol*, 8(3), 2021.
5. Alikulovich, M. K. (2022). Method of developing speed-strength qualities in young swimmers 12-14 years. *Modern Journal of Social Sciences and Humanities*, 4, 179-182.
6. Akbar, A. (2021). Rationality In Moral Philosophy Husayn Kashifi. *European Journal of Humanities and Educational Advancements*, 2(10), 132-134.
- Raimov, K. S. (2024). Influence of sports exercise on women's health. *Modern Scientific Research International Scientific Journal*, 2(3), 103-110.
7. Soatovich, R. X. (2020). Development of Didactic Support for the Preparation of Future Physical Education Teachers for Innovative Activities in the Field of Womens Sport Education. *JournalNX*, 132-135.
8. Turdimurodov, D. Y. (2024). About the volitional qualities of a human and the bases for their identification. *Modern Scientific Research International Scientific Journal*, 2(2), 103-108.
9. Soatovich, R. H. (2023). Empowering Girls for Future Pedagogical Leadership: Understanding Didactic Principles. *Best Journal of Innovation in Science, Research and Development*, 2(12), 598-601.
10. Haqqulov, A. A. (2022). Jismoniy tarbiya darislarida jismoniy tarbiya vositalaridan samarali foydalanish metodlari. *Results of National Scientific Research International Journal*, 1(7), 425-432.
11. Hakkulov, A. A. (2021). The dynamics of the development of strength qualities in volleyball classes with students of physical education. *Theoretical & Applied science Учредители: Теоретическая и прикладная наука*, (9), 765-767.

12. Hakkulov, A. A. (2024). Training volleyball techniques in higher education institutions. *Modern Scientific Research International Scientific Journal*, 2(2), 138-144.
13. Menglikulov, K. A. (2024). Application of innovative methods in the process of teaching swimming to preschool children. *Modern Scientific Research International Scientific Journal*, 2(2), 131-137.
14. Абдуллаев, Я. М., & Турдимуродов, Д. Й. (2020). Ўсмир ёшдаги ўқувчиларда продавий сифатларни жисмоний тарбия воситалари орқали ривожлантириш. *Современное образование (Узбекистан)*, (9 (94)), 56-62.
15. Абдуллаев, Я. М., & Турдимуродов, Д. Ю. (2020). Создание педагогических условий в формировании волевых качеств у учеников начальных классов. In *Colloquium-journal* (No. 24-2, pp. 14-16). Голопристанський міськрайонний центр зайнятості= Голопристанский районный центр занятости.
16. Maxkamovich, A. Y., & Abdukahorovich, S. K. (2019). Modern approaches to the content of physical education of schoolchildren in the continuing education system. *European Journal of Research and Reflection in Educational Sciences Vol*, 7(12).
17. Менгликулов, Х. А. Актуальные научные исследования в современном мире. *Актуальные научные исследования в современном мире, Учредители: Общественная организация. Институт социальной трансформации*, 104-107.